

INNOVATIVE EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Annotation. This article discusses the use of innovative pedagogical technologies used in the educational process

Keywords: pedagogy, innovative activity, innovative technologies, personality-oriented technologies, student-centered approach, special atmosphere

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается применение инновационных педагогических технологий применяемые в учебном процессе

Ключевые слова: педагогика, инновационная деятельность, инновационные технологии, личностно-ориентированные технологии, студ-ориентированный особая атмосфера.

The teacher today faces new challenges and new opportunities open up, taking into account their application.

The concept of "innovation" in foreign literature is defined in different ways, depending on different methodological approaches - Technology is a tool for the professional activity of a teacher.

The essence of pedagogical technology lies in the fact that it has a pronounced phasing (step by step).

Innovative activity is a special kind of pedagogical activity. Innovations define new methods, forms, means, technologies used in pedagogical practice, focused on the personality of the child, on the development of his abilities. Innovative technologies are a system of methods, ways, methods of teaching, educational means aimed at achieving a positive result due to dynamic changes in the student's personal development in modern socio-cultural conditions. The use of modern educational

technologies ensures the flexibility of the educational process, increases the cognitive interest of students, and increases creative activity.

In my teaching practice I use the following innovative educational technologies:

- health-saving;
- technology of project activities;
- developing;
- corrective;
- information and communication;
- technologies of research activity;
- personality-oriented;
- gaming;
- teacher portfolio technology.

Project activity: its meaning is to create a problematic activity, which is carried out by the student together with the teacher. The knowledge that a student receives in the course of working on a project becomes his personal property and is firmly fixed in the existing system of knowledge about the world around him. The main goal of the project method is the development of a free creative personality, which is determined by the tasks of development and the tasks of the research activities of students.

Projects vary:

- by the number of participants: individual, pair, group, frontal;
- by duration: short-term, medium-term, long-term;
- according to the priority method: creative, game, research, information;
- by subject: include the student's family, nature, society, cultural values and more.

Information and communication technologies have received their natural development in our "advanced" age. A situation where a student would not know what a computer is is practically unrealistic. With the help of exciting programs for teaching reading and mathematics, for the development of memory and logic, students manage to interest the "sciences". The computer has a number of significant advantages over

the classical lesson. Animated pictures flashing on the screen attract the student and allow them to concentrate their attention. With the help of computer programs, it becomes possible to simulate various life situations. Depending on the student's abilities, the program can be tailored specifically for him, that is, to focus on his individual development. Examples of forms of classes using information and communication technologies: Lesson-visualization - the presentation of the content is accompanied by a presentation (demonstration of educational materials presented in various sign systems, including illustrative, graphic, audio and video materials). Practical lesson in the form of a presentation - presentation of the results of project or research activities using specialized software tools. The tasks of teachers: to keep up with the times, to become a guide for the student in the world of new technologies, a mentor in choosing computer programs, to form the foundations of the information culture of his personality, to improve the professional level of teachers and the competence of parents. ICT in the work of a modern teacher is:

- selection of illustrative material;
- exchange of experience, acquaintance with periodicals;
- preparation of group documentation, reports - selection of materials for classes;
- Familiarity with scenarios;
- creation of presentations

Correctional technologies: their purpose is to relieve the psycho-emotional stress of students.

Types: - technology of musical influence (music therapy);

- art therapy;
- logarithmics;
- fairy tale therapy;
- color therapy;

Cognitive research activity: the main goal is to create an experimental activity, in which the student is an active participant. The direct participation of the student during the experiment allows him to see the process and results with his own eyes. When

organizing these technologies, pupils are offered a problematic task that can be solved by researching something or conducting experiments. Methods and methods of organizing this activity are:

- conversations;
- observations;
- modeling;
- fixing the results;
- Didactic games, game training and creatively developing situations;
- Job assignments, actions.

Personality-oriented technologies are technologies that put the personality of the child at the center of the educational system, providing it with comfortable, conflict-free, safe conditions for development. Provides for the preparation of individual educational programs that meet the needs and abilities of each individual student. The purpose of this technology is to create democratic partner humanistic relations between a student and a teacher.¹

With a student-centered approach, the student's personality is put at the head of learning. Morning gathering as a way of organizing free verbal communication Goals and tasks of the morning gathering:

- develop skills (communication, planning one's own activities, etc.);
- learn to explain your emotional state in words;
- develop cultural communication skills (greetings, compliments, etc.);
- to teach to formulate judgments, to argue statements, to defend one's point of view;
- choose from personal experience the most significant, interesting events, talk about them briefly, consistently and logically;
- learn to make choices, as well as plan your own activities. Game technology.

Practice shows that the lesson is using game situations.

¹ Абдуллаева Х.А. Машгулотларда фаол таълим усулларидан фойдаланиш. – Фарғона: ФарДУ, 2008.
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In such classes, a special atmosphere develops, where there are elements of creativity and free choice. The ability to work in a group develops: its victory depends on the personal efforts of each. At the same time, games have many cognitive, educational functions. Among the game exercises, one can distinguish those

- which help to highlight the characteristic features of objects: that is, they teach to compare;
- which help to generalize objects according to certain characteristics;
- which teach the student to separate fiction from reality;
- which bring up communication in a team, develop speed of reaction, ingenuity and more.

Having studied the characteristics of each student, I believe that each student is unique in his individuality and has the right to develop at his own pace, along his own educational trajectory. There are different students in the group, with different levels of development. When applying technology, I divide students into conditional groups, taking into account typological features. When dividing into groups, I take into account the personal attitude of students to the surrounding reality, the degree of mastering the program material, and interest in learning new material. Education is returning to the formula "we study not for the university, but for life."²

When conducting classes, I use computer technology as a way of presenting and facilitating the process of perception and memorization of information with the help of vivid images, the development of memory, thinking, and attention. As a result of the combination of educational and gaming activities, students learn to model the material, independently extract knowledge. This form of work helps to instill students' interest in the proposed topics and maintain it in the future. Communication with a computer causes students - first as a game, and then as an educational activity. In this case, the use of computer technology becomes especially appropriate, as it provides information

² Е. А. Калюжный, Ю. Трёмаскина, Д. Борзенко, Е. Норкина, К. Глаголева, К. Розина, А. Любаев // Современные научные исследования и инновации. 2014. № 10–2 (42). С. 175–179.

in an attractive form, which not only speeds up memorization, but also makes it meaningful and long-term. The use of innovative pedagogical technologies contributes to:

- improving the quality of education;
- improving the qualifications of educators;
- application of pedagogical experience and its systematization;
- use of computer technologies by pupils;
- maintaining and strengthening the health of pupils;
- improving the quality of education and upbringing.

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